

Features of Measles Progression in Adults at the Modern Stage

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Relevance: Measles remains a significant public health issue, particularly in countries with low vaccination coverage. In recent years, an increase in measles cases has been observed, including among adults, due to vaccine hesitancy and lack of immunity.

The aim of the study: To investigate the clinical and laboratory characteristics of measles in adults and identify differences compared to children.

Materials and methods: Observations were conducted on 208 patients (152 adults and 56 children) diagnosed with measles. Clinical, serological, and statistical analysis methods were utilized. Measles-specific antibody levels were determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Results: Measles in adults is more severe compared to children: The proportion of severe cases among adults was 13.1% (compared to 8.9% in children). Mild forms were less frequent in adults, at 5.9% (compared to 35.7% in children). Adults showed more pronounced intoxication and febrile responses. Complications, such as bronchitis, were more common (69.7% of cases). Adults exhibited less severe catarrhal symptoms during the catarrhal stage, but these differences disappeared during the rash stage. A significant proportion of adults (60%) lacked confirmed information about their vaccination status, complicating the assessment of vaccine influence.

Conclusions: Measles in adults retains its typical symptoms but is characterized by more severe progression and a higher rate of complications compared to children. Diagnosis relies on clinical manifestations, epidemiological history, and laboratory testing. Vaccination remains a critical preventive measure; however, low vaccination coverage increases the risk of infection spread.

Practical Implications: The study emphasizes the importance of increasing vaccination coverage, particularly among adults, and the need for timely diagnosis and hospitalization to prevent severe cases and complications.